

González, F., Moreno, C., Santos, A. (2006). The Massive Sulfide Event in the Iberian Pyrite Belt: confirmatory evidence from the Sotiel-Coronada Mine. Geological Magazine, 143, 821-827.

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Abstract:

Well-preserved miospore and organic-walled microphytoplankton assemblages have been recovered from the black shaly series hosting the massive sulphide deposits of Sotiel-Coronada Mine (Iberian Pyrite Belt). The productive samples yielded miospore assemblages representing the uppermost Famennian *Retispora lepidophyta*–*Verrucosisorites nitidus* (LN) miospore Biozone of Western Europe. This palynological evidence has important implications for the local geology, constraining the commencement of the volcanic activity and corroborating the previously-defined local tectonic style. Moreover, at regional scale, the new data permit correlation of the black shaly series (which hosts the mineralization in all the sulphide deposits hitherto dated in the region), reinforcing the hypothesis of an anoxic event occurring in the Iberian Pyrite Belt in the latest Devonian times.

Key words:

Devonian, Iberian Pyrite Belt, Sotiel-Coronada Mine, Spain, palynology, black shales